

Chemical Characterisation of *Eucalyptus kirtoniana* Seed Oil

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Seed oil from *Eucalyptus kirtoniana* was analysed for physico-chemical characteristics and fatty acid composition. The seed oil was rich in oleic acid and no unusual fatty acid was found.

LOCALISED shortages of traditional edible oils¹ have focused attention on the unconventional non-edible oils for their useful exploitation in recent times². These minor non-edible oils, however, need to be investigated chemically prior to their exploitation. A number of studies on chemical characterisation of these minor non-edible oils have recently been reported³⁻¹¹. In our laboratory, we have also started a systematic study on the chemical characterisation of these minor oils. As a part of our investigation, seed oil from *Eucalyptus kirtoniana* was analysed for physico-chemical characteristics and fatty acid composition.

Experimental

The mature fruits of *Eucalyptus kirtoniana* (Myrtaceae) were collected from the local forests of Burdwan and the seeds were removed from air-dried fruits. The seeds were powdered and the oil was extracted in a soxhlet apparatus using n-hexane. Physicochemical constants were determined according to the reported methods¹². The seed oil was saponified at 110° for 12 h in ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution and unsaponifiable matters were extracted from the soap solution with ether. Saponified fatty acids were acidified, extracted with ether and the free fatty acids were then converted into their methyl esters with diazomethane. The mixture of methyl esters were applied to a 150 g diethylene glycol succinate (DEGS)/kg chromosorb WHMDS column of a Perkin-Elmer F11 gas liquid chromatograph for fatty acid analysis. The conditions employed were: column length 4 m, column temperature 200°, injection temperature 300°, attenuation

32×100, carrier gas nitrogen, speed of the carrier gas 2.6 kg/h and chart speed 60 cm/h. The peaks were identified using the reference compounds under the same conditions. The peak area percentages were considered as weight percentage.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical characteristics of the seed oil and its fatty acid composition are presented in Table 1. It is seen that the seeds contained 29% oil. So this seed is worth commercial exploitation.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTIC AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF *Eucalyptus kirtoniana* SEED OIL*

Oil content of the seed	29%
Colour	dark red
Unsaponifiable matter	3.2%
Saponification value	197
Iodine value (Wij's)	102
Acid value	9.5%
Fatty acids (glc, DEGS column, %)	
Lauric (12 : 0)	0.7
Myristic (14 : 0)	3.4
Palmitic (16 : 0)	4.3
Stearic (18 : 0)	13.4
Arachidic (20 : 0)	2.1
Behenic (22 : 0)	4.5
Oleic (18 : 1)	50.4
Linoleic (18 : 2)	14.8
Linolenic (18 : 3)	6.4

*Average of four readings.

In our earlier studies, it has been shown that this deoiled seed cake is fairly good source of protein and may be used in animal feed formulations after ascertaining its non-toxicity¹³⁻¹⁵. The seed oil

contained no oxygenated fatty acids, such as epoxy, keto or hydroxy acids as revealed by glc. The high unsaponifiable matter, the high acid value and dark visible colour are some of the undesirable factors which can be easily removed by bleaching, deodourisation and refining.

The glc analysis showed the presence of only usual fatty acids in the seed oil. The seed oil is rich in oleic acid and contained significant proportion of linoleic acid. Thus, this seed oil appears promising for exploitation as a source of oleic acid-rich oil for use in the manufacture of soap and fatty acids. The seed oil may also be used for edible purposes after ascertaining its non-toxicity. Processing and biological testing of this seed oil are in progress in our laboratory.

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